
MILITARY APPLICATIONS OF COMPUTER VARIOUS TO ELECTRONIC WARFARE

By

ABUBAKAR S. YARO

*Department of Computer Science School of Sciences
Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin*

Abstract

Computer viruses are mysterious and draw our attention. On the one hand, viruses show us how vulnerable we are. A properly engineered virus can have an amazing effect on the worldwide internet and on the other hand viruses show us how sophisticated and interconnected human beings have become.

Most military formations use viruses to attack their enemy country. This paper will be a useful guide to military formations for combat readiness. It will also be a guide to large organizations, institutions and individuals to install anti virus tools and scan through the systems from time to time to check virus attack so as to know them. Since people who listen to different ideas on the risk of offences and uses at least consider that they might be wrong, cannot but gain from this paper.

INTRODUCTION

A computer virus is a program that requires a host in order to make copies of itself on computer disk. Computer viruses are small programs that attach themselves to computer applications and wreck havoc on them. They are programs that spread when infected files are transferred from one computer to another. A virus program will associate itself with another program so that when the program is started, the virus is released at the same time. Some viruses actively destroy software or entire computer system and render it unusable. Some can delete files, some open up a door way to let hackers into the network undetected. Some can be used to initiate denial of service, some cause texts or graphics to be displayed where they are not wanted, some slow down a computer's communications and processing capabilities, while some

just sit there and do not do much of anything. They can cause some significant economic damage.

A computer virus is thus a code that attaches itself to other programs in order to alter their behavior often in a harmful way. Viruses do not care where they are got from, either as an e mail attachment, a download or via a shared disk. Once an infected file or application is opened, the malicious code copies itself into files of the system where they are opened and wait to deliver its payload whatever the programmer designed it to do to a computer system. Simply deleting the e mail after opening the attachment will not get rid of the virus, since it has already entered the computer system where it was opened. A virus writer can set the payload to trigger immediately, at a preset future time or date or upon the execution of a specified command such as SAVE or OPEN a file. The Michel Angelo virus for example was programmed to release its payload on March 6th of every year, the birthday of the writer.

As intranets and internet have grown in proportion, e mail has evolved from a convenience to a necessity. Virus's vandals know that and they have invented new ways to use e mail to spread viruses especially worms. A worm program replicates itself and spreads through network connections to infect any computer on the network and replicate itself with it, eating up storage space and slowing down the computer. Worm programs have the potential for sabotage, extortion or blackmail. The name worm was coined as an analogue to a tape worm, a parasitic creature that lives in the intestines of infected human beings and other vertebrates. However, they tend to consume large amount of resources for their own dissemination, thus denying services to legitimate users. The usual lines of attack are the users' mailing lists which contain the names and addresses of other reachable computers. After gaining access to a mailing list, the worm sends copies of itself to some other or all listed computers. The infection usually spreads quickly and downs the entire system by consuming time and network bandwidth so that little or no other work and communication can proceed.

When a person clicks on the attachment, the worm is launched, and then spreads itself by mass mailing itself to all the e mail addresses listed on the infected computers.

DEFENCES AND OUTLOOK AGAINST VIRUSES

Defenses against viruses take generally one or three forms:

i. ACTIVITY MONITORS

Activity monitors are programs that are resident on the system. They monitor activity and either raises a warning or take special action in the event of suspicious activity. Thus, attempt to alter the interrupt table in the memory or to rewrite the boot sector will be intercepted by such monitors. This form of defense can be circumvented by viruses which activate earlier in the boot sector sequence than the monitor code. Another form of monitors are the ones that emulate or otherwise trace execution of a suspect application. The monitor will evaluate the actions taken by the code and determine if any of the activities are similar to that a virus would undertake. Appropriate warnings are issued if suspicious activity is identified.

ii. SCANNERS

Scanners have been the most popular and widespread form of virus defenses. A scanner operates by reading data from disk and applying pattern matching operation against a list of known virus pattern. If a match is found for a pattern, a virus instance is announced. Scanners are fast and easy to use but they suffer from many disadvantages. Among them is that the list of patterns must be kept up to date. In the MS WORD, new viruses are appearing by as many as several dozen each day and week. Keeping patterns file up to date in this rapidly damaging environment is very difficult. Another reason is one of false positive report. As more patterns are added to the list, it becomes more likely that one of them will match some otherwise legitimate code. Again, polymorphic viruses cannot be detected by scanners.

To the advantage of scanners, however, is their spread. Scanners can be made

to work quickly. They can also be done portably and across platforms which are easy to distribute and update. Of the new virus discovered each week, few will become widespread. Scanners equipped with algorithms or heuristic checking may also find most polymorphic viruses. Scanner software looks for a virus in one or two ways. If the virus is known, the software will look for the virus signature that is a unique string of bytes that identify the virus like a finger print and will ZAP it from the system.

iii. **INTEGRITY CHECKERS**

These are programs that generate check codes e.g checksums cyclic redundancy code in C.P.U, secure hashes, message digits or cryptographic checksums for monitoring files. These checksums or codes are recomputed against the saved. If the comparison fails, a check is known ve occurred to the file and it is flagged for further investigation Integrity monitors run continuously and check the integrity of files on regular basis. The shells check codes prior to every execution. Integrity check is an almost certain way to discover alteration to files including data files. As viruses must alter files to implant themselves, integrity checking will find those changes. Integrity checkers may also find changes caused by buggy software problems in hardware and operator errors. If the self check reveal some unexpected change in memory or on disk, the program will terminate or warn the user. This helps to signal the presence of a virus quickly so that further actions may be taken.

MILITARY APPLICATION OF VIRUSES IN ELECTRONIC WARFARE

Events of the last few years demonstrated dramatically that computer viruses are not feasible but can quickly cause catastrophic disruption of computer systems and networks. Systems have significantly increased the vulnerability of these systems to computer virus attack This has created a new form of electronic warfare consisting in the electronic infections of computer virus micro code into a victim electronic system through direct or indirect mechanism (Myron and Patt, 2006).

DEFENSE ELECTRONIC

Military electronic systems have historically included a wide variety of sensors, control systems, communications and electronic warfare equipments, sensors include radars, inferred systems. Electro optical systems and lasers that fill many critical functions including monitoring system operation and target development. Control systems include navigation anti pilot systems, guidance systems and stabilizer systems. Communication systems provide connecting among participants for distribution of mission tasking and exchange of data. Increased automation of weapon systems have led to greater uses of computerized digital communications

ELECTRONIC WARFARE

The field of electronic warfare has evolved to develop techniques and systems to deny an adversary the use of the electromagnetic spectrum and to protect their uses. Electronic warfare systems provide threat warning platform, self protection and counter measures against threats for systems using the electromagnetic spectrum.

The infamous gulf war virus hoax has continued to inflate the threat of info war in the gulf war. The U. S. A. implanted viruses and other computer intrusion into IRAQI air defenses. The National Security Agency developed viruses and smuggled them into IRAQI, from France hidden in a chip of a printer. The virus was said to disable IRAQI air defense computers by devouring the Windows opened on computers screens. In the days following the gulf war, information warfare weapons had been unleashed on the IRAQI air defenses. According to the account, France printers exported to the IRAQI military were intercepted by the National Security Agency of U. S. A. On these chips were programs designed to infect and interrupt the communication systems that linked anti aircraft missiles to radar installations. However, the virus did not get a chance much to do its job because the U.S.A. Air force accidentally bombed the building where IRAQI stored the printers. It would be noted that computer viruses have the potential to operate by targeting the victim's

system processors and can be used to target a wider set of electronic systems (John Arquilla, 2009). However, since computer viruses exploit the victim's processors, the manner in which they achieve their effect is different. Additionally, computer viruses can be used to target wider set of weapon system functions. Several recent trends in the military electronic systems have contributed to the increased viability of computer viruses in electronic warfare. These include, increased use of distributed digital processing, Re programmable embedded computers, Networked communications, computer standardization, software standardization, standard message formats and data.

One of the challenging aspects of developing and employing computer viruses in electronic warfare is the ability to effectively inject the virus in the target equipment. To be effective, the computer virus must be placed so that it can propagate and infect the systems. Computer viruses possess unique characteristics that can be exploited for circumvent a majority of the protective schemes. Potentially, the most useful characteristics of computer viruses used in electronic warfare are that:

- i. The effect of the virus continue after source system has been turned off
- ii. Viruses propagate from system to system.

Using these characteristics, there are four (4) mechanisms by which viruses can enter enemy systems. These are Front and Back door coupling, Direct and Indirect coupling.

FRONT DOOR COUPLING

This is the way of accessing the target by using the media for which the system was designed. Like the front door coupling to an ordinary tactical radio would use electromagnetic waves directed at the antenna and receivers. Electronic computer viruses can attack the weakest link in the target's defenses while traditional electronic counter measures must be to detect the strongest link in the receiver defenses

BACK DOOR COUPLING

This is the way any technique is used to access the target systems is designed. The system has either direct or indirect electronic coupling to system processors. One approach that has been proposed is to infect viruses via carefully controlled electromagnetic spikes into the target systems. Other back door coupling techniques include components designed tempering and other form of espionage.

VIRUS JAMMING STRATEGIES

Computer viruses may be employed within several jamming strategies. These include:

a. TROJAN HORSE STRATEGY

The Trojan horse strategy is just what the name implies. The virus is injected into the target system and lies dormant until a pre assigned event or time and then it causes the catastrophic damage or deception to the system or network in which it resides. The advantage of the strategy is that the virus has no effect until a desired event occur so it does not raise suspicion.

b. FORCED QUARANTINE STRATEGY

This is used to target Networks. The virus would enter networks and announce itself. This will force networks to operate as independent nodes, generally reducing their effectiveness.

c. OVERLOAD STRATEGY

This will simply duplicate itself many times and slow down the processing speed of the systems. This added delay in the processor may be tremendous degradation in time sensitive systems, such as the control radars

d. PROBE STRATEGY

This would search for a specific piece of data and then transmit itself back to a

specified location. This will allow highly targeted exploitation for critical piece of information.

e. ASSIGN STRATEGY

This would be injected in a network for destroying one particular file system or other entity. It would propagate and then erase itself in all locations until it find the target. The virus would then disable the target and erase itself one final time, leaving no trace.

TOOLS NEEDED FOR WRITING VIRUS CODES

Viruses are written in Assembly language. High Level Languages, like BASIC, C, and PASCAL etc have been designed to generate stand alone programming but the assumptions made by these languages render them almost useless when writing viral codes. They are simply incapable for performing the acrobatics required for a virus to jump from one host program to the job but no one has done it yet. Thus, to create viruses, one must use assembly language. It is just the only way we can get exciting control over all the computer system's resources and use them the way we want to do, rather than the way somebody think we should. It is assumed that to write a virus program, one should have knowledge of assembly language or to understand how it functions, at least at the level where it can be understood about some of the basic machine instructions like MOV, AX, BX do. As for those that are not familiar with simple assembly language, or the resources to buy one or the inclination to learn assembly language, the viruses' basics are provided in INTEL, HEX Format, so they can be directly loaded into the computer in executable format. The program disk also contains compiled directly to executable version of each virus (Ludviz, 2008).

CONCLUSIONS

Over the last years, computer viruses have gone from an academic curiosity to a persistent worldwide problem that viruses can be written for on virtually any computing platform. The world is full of computer viruses that are commonly trying to penetrate the semi - permeable bounding that segregates the organizations from external world. It is important that anti virus software detects viruses that have been observed in the wild world. We must always be prepared for the possibility that low profile viruses will start to become prevalent. This requires administrators to be familiar with all viruses, prevalent or not and to incorporate a knowledge of as many of them as possible into the anti virus software.

Implementing virus defense procedures is an integral part of system administrator's job. These procedures should be integrated with other chores such as backing up the network servers. Scan for viruses should be performed regularly using good anti virus software. Some new viruses appear unpredictable infernos and old viruses mutate, it is important to update our anti virus software regularly. There are several websites on the internet to download anti virus software on a regular basis. All back up files must be kept in fire proof rooms so that when data of the organization is lost due to virus attack, the administrator can reinstall the data back to the systems.

It is important that priority should be given to enhanced performance improvement in evolutionary codes to make automated bypassing of protection mechanism very complex Computer virus can hoop form machine to machine accomplishing the goals programmed into it, with none to control it, and so it becomes a viable form of electronic life.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar S. Yaro (2005) : Basic issues in computer viruses, A paper presented on guided reading to the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, LAUTECH, OGBOMOSO, UNPUBLISHED
- Adio Olayinka : Implications of system failure, Daily Times, Tuesday, February 23rd, 1999, pg14
- Eugene H. Spafford (2009) : The internet Worm crisis and aftermath, Communications of ACM, June 2009
- Fred Cohen (2005) : Computer viruses, Ph. D thesis, University of Southern California, unpublished
- John and Heyness (2009) : Computer virus, Worms, Data Diddlers and other threats to systems, Washington, ST. Mantus press
- Klim Zetter (2002) : How computer viruses work, PC WORLD W. A Pg 65-69
- Peter J. Demny (2008) Computer under attack : Intruders, worms and viruses, ACM Press V.Y.
- Phillips F. Peter (2005) The computer virus crisis. VanNostrand, Renhold, U. S.A.
- Steve Levy (2002) : Artificial Life, the quest for a new creation, Patheon, N.Y.
- Sussan Keller (1999) : Adapso urges computer Act on viruses, Washington Technology, U. S.A.
- U. S.A. Airforce (2007) : Architecture Specification for Piller Avionks : Specification SPA9009001E.